

On the Orness of Bonferroni mean and its variants

Bapi Dutta^{a,*}, José Rui Figueira^b, Satyajit Das^c

^a*The Logistics Institute Asia Pacific, National University of Singapore, 21 Heng Mui Keng Terrace, 119613, Singapore.*

^b*CEG-IST, Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa, Portugal.*

^c*Department of Mathematics, Adamas University, Kolkata-700126.*

Abstract

This article addresses orness measures to reflect the or-like degree of the Bonferroni mean (BM) and its variants. Some properties of these operators associated with their orness measures are portrayed analytically. However, the general orness measure involves the multiple integrals with the integral fold number being the number of the aggregated elements and as a result, the computation becomes complicated when the number of the aggregated elements is large. Furthermore, the analytical formula of the orness measure often cannot be obtained. For this reason, this study concentrates on Monte Carlo simulation to validate the result. We estimate the two parameters of the BM for a predefined orness value and a fixed length of the input vector. Besides the theoretical study of orness measure related to BM and its variants, the article also explores the simulation-based results. To support this, we provide four numerical examples.

Keywords: Aggregation operator, Orness measure, Bonferroni mean, Monte Carlo simulation, Decision making

1. Introduction

The orness value of an aggregation operator measures in which degree the aggregation operator behaves as maximum operator or as minimum operator. The orness measure can also be interpreted as the mode of decision making in the aggregation process due to its attitudinal character. The orness measure was first introduced by Dujmovic¹ in 1974 for power root-means under the name of disjunction degree and this work is a landmark in this direction. In 1988, Yager² introduced the orness measure in an independent way (together with a dual measure called andness) by taking into account the similarity of the OWA operator with the maximum (and minimum, respectively) operator when a particular weighting vector is used. The same author suggests that, based on Hurwicz's model,⁴ the measure of orness can be interpreted as a measure of optimism of the decision making, while the measure of andness is a measure of pessimism.³ On the other hand, Arnould and Ralescu⁵ introduced a probabilistic interpretation of this measure. Later, Marichal⁶ proved that the orness measure can be defined for any compensatory aggregation operator. In recent time, some properties of this measure of orness have been discussed.^{7,8} Legarreta et al.⁹ extended the concept of orness to the framework of idempotent aggregation

*Corresponding author

Email addresses: bapi.iitr@gmail.com (Bapi Dutta), figueira@tecnico.ulisboa.pt (José Rui Figueira), satyajitnit.das@gmail.com (Satyajit Das)

functions defined on the real unit interval and on a complete lattice with a local finiteness condition. Based on Dujmović's studies, Fodor et al.¹⁰ proposed the orness index of any mean operator. In this direction, Torra¹¹ also shows that how orness degree does not even have to be restricted to the field of aggregation operators.

The OWA operator² has received considerable attention from the researchers of the intelligent system community and obtained meaningful results.^{12–16} One of the appealing points of OWA operator is the notion of orness.² The orness measure reflects the and-like or or-like aggregation result of an OWA operator, which is very important both in theory and practical applications.^{17–22} Liu²³ proposed a general optimization model to obtain the consistency of OWA operator family by changing the orness level. However, one important observation regarding Yager's orness is the lack of categorization of orness and andness. Without using the orness formula it is impossible to say whether the aggregation is or-like or and-like. To elaborate this, Kishore et al.²⁴ provide an axiomatic definition of orness with more plausible features and better categorization. Recently, Paternain et al.²⁵ introduced a quantitative measure of orness for OWA operator on the basis of its proximity to the OR operator.

Nowadays, some academic research analyses have focused on the extension of Yager's orness concept to other aggregation operators and subsequently developed by other researchers. For example, based on the given orness measure,² O'Hagon²⁶ used the maximum entropy method to obtain OWA operator weights which is also called maximum entropy OWA (MEOWA) operator. Rongxi and Jianrong²⁷ proposed a process for obtaining weights of MEOWA operator by using uncertain orness measure. Torra²⁸ studied the orness of the weighted OWA operator. An extension of the original orness definition has also proposed by Salido and Murakami.²⁹ Liu³⁰ defined the orness degree of the quasi-arithmetic mean operator by using the generating function representation method. Liu³¹ proposed two orness indices to reflect the or-like level of the quasi-OWA operator and Bajraktarević mean by using generating functions.

It is worth noticing that, sometimes the different OWA operators have the same orness value and this may create problems in application situations. In this circumstance, fuzzy orness measure is useful to supplement Yager's orness measure to overcome this issue. Thus, the orness measure has also extended to imprecise environment. For example, Salido and Murakami²⁹ extended the Yager's orness concept to the fuzzy mean aggregators. Jin et al.³² proposed a fuzzy orness measure based on the inner product of lattice operations.

From the practical application viewpoint, orness measure has also attracted many researchers and some of the recent publications^{25,33–37} are strong evidence of it. For example, Dujmović³³ investigated the orness and andness as the mean of overall importance of arguments. Carlson et al.³⁸ applied the orness measure for decision making in fuzzy ontology. Yu and Reiff³⁹ applied orness measure to logic scoring preference method for automated web service selection. Aggregation of edge weights in social networks extracted from multiple sources with different importance degrees is investigated by Alguliev et al.³⁶. The orness of OWA operator can be used to represent the preference information in aggregation problems too.^{40,41} Aristondo and Ciommi³⁷ presented the degree of orness for the poverty measures of the poverty gap ratio and in this work they have shown that the value of orness has a natural application in welfare economics.

Based on the above research landscape of related literature review, it has been observed that, orness measure of OWA and *quasi*-arithmetic mean have been proposed by bypassing complex n -fold integral involving the definition of orness proposed by Dujmović¹. However, the connection of orness measure with Bonferroni mean (BM) and its variants, has not yet been attended so far. This observation motivates us to focus on the systematic investigation of orness measure related to BM and its variants. For this purpose, in this work, we address the problem of computing the orness of BM, Geometric BM (GBM) and partitioned BM (PBM) operators. To do this, we first systematically investigate behaviour of BM and its variants with respect to their associated parameters and length of the input as they influence the orness of these aggregation operators. The associated properties of the BM and its variants are discussed to show the behaviour of orness measures. To validate the obtained results, Monte Carlo simulation is utilized. Moreover, from the practical application perspective of this aggregation operators, we investigate the estimation of the parameters p and q associated with BM and its variants for a given value of the orness and fixed length of the input vector. Results are also analyzed via suitable examples.

The structure of this manuscript is as follows: Section 2 begins with reviews of the orness and andness measures. This section also discusses how orness measure defined by Liu,³¹ significantly differs from the original orness measure. Section 3 proposes orness measures of BM and its variants, particularly, we concentrate our study on defining orness measure of BM, GBM and PBM operators. Section 4 analyzes the results by utilizing suitable examples. The simulation results have also incorporated in this section. Furthermore, this section illustrates the orness measure in an algorithmic fashion. Section 5 summarizes the obtained results and draws conclusions.

2. A brief review of the process of measuring orness

In this section, we carry out a brief discussion about the concepts of the important numerical characteristics of averaging aggregation functions, namely, orness and andness, that will be useful for our subsequent developments.

2.1. On orness measure

Generally, aggregation function can be classified into four major categories: conjunctive, disjunctive, averaging and uninorm type (which exhibit different behaviours in different parts of the domain of aggregation function).^{42,43} Among them, the class of averaging functions is the most used one in real world applications.⁴⁴ Therefore, it is necessary to understand the behaviour of averaging functions. In this respect, Dujmovic,¹ introduced the concept of two indices, namely, *andness* and orness that offer a better understanding of general behavior of aggregation function with respect to its variables. The *andness* degree of an aggregation operator F indicates that the degree to which F is close to *Min* function. On the other hand, the orness degree signifies the closeness of an aggregation function to *Max* function. Formally, the orness and *andness* degrees can be given in the following way:^{42,43}

Definition 1. Let $\mathbf{a}_n \in [0, 1]^n$ be an input vector. The orness of an aggregation function $F : [0, 1]^n \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is defined as

$$\text{orness}(F(\mathbf{a}_n)) = \frac{\int_{[0,1]^n} F(\mathbf{a}_n) - \int_{[0,1]^n} \min(\mathbf{a}_n)}{\int_{[0,1]^n} \max(\mathbf{a}_n) - \int_{[0,1]^n} \min(\mathbf{a}_n)} \quad (1)$$

Definition 2. Let $\mathbf{a}_n \in [0, 1]^n$ be an input vector. The andness of an aggregation function $F : [0, 1]^n \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is defined as

$$\text{andness}(F(\mathbf{a}_n)) = \frac{\int_{[0,1]^n} \max(\mathbf{a}_n) - \int_{[0,1]^n} F(\mathbf{a}_n)}{\int_{[0,1]^n} \max(\mathbf{a}_n) - \int_{[0,1]^n} \min(\mathbf{a}_n)} \quad (2)$$

It is not much difficult to find the andness and orness measure of simple aggregation function like, arithmetic mean (AM), geometric mean (GM) and OWA operator as we can easily evaluate the n -fold integral $\int_{[0,1]^n} F(\mathbf{a}_n)$. According to Eq. (1), the orness of the AM ($AM(\mathbf{a}_n) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n a_i$) is $\text{orness}(AM(\mathbf{a}_n)) = \frac{1}{2}$, i.e, it is neither and-like nor or-like. Similarly, the orness of the GM ($GM(\mathbf{a}_n) = (\prod_{i=1}^n a_i)^{1/n}$) is given by

$$\text{orness}(GM(\mathbf{a}_n)) = \left(\frac{n}{n+1} \right)^{n-1} \frac{n}{n-1} - \frac{1}{n-1} \quad (3)$$

Clearly, the orness of GM depends only on the input dimension/length of the input set. However, the computation of orness level becomes very challenging issue when the aggregation function F takes a little complicated form and consequently the evaluation of $\int_{[0,1]^n} F(\mathbf{a}_n)$ becomes very difficult. To the best of our knowledge, in most of the cases finding the analytic form is almost impossible. For example, the power arithmetic, which can be defined as

Definition 3. For an input vector $\mathbf{a}_n = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) \in [0, 1]^n$, the quasi-arithmetic mean can be defined as a mapping $M_\phi : [0, 1]^n \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and given by

$$M_\phi(\mathbf{a}_n) = \phi^{-1} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \phi(a_i) \right) \quad (4)$$

where $\phi(\cdot)$ is a continuous, strictly monotone function, called generator of the *quasi*-arithmetic mean M_ϕ .

When $\phi(a) = a^r$, we obtain the power arithmetic mean and it is not possible to find the analytical form of the orness measure by using the Eq. (1). To overcome this issue, some of the approaches have been proposed in the literature^{30,31} for quasi-arithmetic mean. They bypass the issue of evaluating the n -fold integral by defining new measure of orness in terms of associated parameters of the aggregation function. Liu³⁰ proposed the orness measure of quasi-arithmetic mean in terms of its generator by avoiding the multiple integrals in Eq. (1) and for the domain $[0, 1]$, it is given by

$$\text{orness}(M_\phi) = \phi^{-1} \left(\int_0^1 \phi(x) dx \right). \quad (5)$$

Although, the orness measure of quasi-arithmetic mean depends on the generators and the length of the input vector, Liu³⁰ shown that the orness measure provides same orness value for any length of the input vector. Further, the orness measure proposed by Liu,³⁰ significantly differs from the original orness measure. We have depicted in Fig. 1 (a) how far the orness measure defined in Eq. (1) differ from Liu's proposed orness measure for a fixed length of the input. It has been observed that, with the gradual increase of the parameters p , the deviation of Liu's orness measure from original orness measure increases. When the generator of the quasi-arithmetic mean is

fixed, the orness measure significantly varies across the length of the input vector and that fact has been depicted in Fig. 1 (b). Moreover, we note that when length of the input vector increases the orness measure approaches to the Liu's orness measure. Further, such approaches of deriving orness measure are very restrictive and class specific. It is not easy to extend for other class of aggregation operators involving more than one parameters with complex structure, such as, BM and its variants.

Figure 1: (a) original orness and Liu's proposed orness for different values of p ; (b) for a fixed p , orness and Liu's orness for different length of input

Therefore, the central issue associated with the measure of orness of BM and variants boil down into the evaluating the n -folds $\int_{[0,1]^n} f$ integral. In these cases, it is quite impossible to derive an analytical form of orness level to our best knowledge. That led us to look for an algorithm which gives a numerical estimate of the integral with an estimate of error. Note that, by fixing the associated parameters values, we may find good numerical estimate of the n -fold integral. For example, one can find numerical estimate of orness of *quasi*-arithmetic mean by fixing the parameter ' r ' of the generator $\phi(x) = x^r$.

2.2. Monte Carlo estimation approach of the n -fold integral

Numerical quadrature rules are useful for one-dimensional integrals. Further, if the integrand is sufficiently smooth and if we know an absolute bound for a certain derivative of the integrand, they produce an exact estimate of the error. The efficiency of numerical quadrature rules decreases rapidly with the number of dimensions.⁴⁵ That fact relies us to consider Monte Carlo integration approach to find the numerical estimate of the orness measure of an aggregation operator.

Monte Carlo integration is a simple and powerful technique for approximating complicated integrals. The basic difference between Monte Carlo integration and other numerical integrations algorithms is that Monte Carlo uses random sampling of the domain of integrands for evaluating the integrand values.⁴⁶ Let us consider the evaluation

of n -dimensional integral

$$I = \int_V f(\mathbf{a}_n) d\mathbf{a}_n. \quad (6)$$

In our case V is a n -dimensional unit hypercube $[0, 1]^n$. The Monte Carlo estimate for the integral I is given by

$$E = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N f(\mathbf{a}_n^k) \quad (7)$$

where N is the number of sampled points in n -dimensional unit hypercube $[0, 1]^n$. The central limit theorem ensures us that the estimate E converges to the true value of the integral, i.e., $N \rightarrow \infty$, $E \rightarrow I$. This gives the estimate of the error $\epsilon = \sigma/\sqrt{N}$, where σ is the variance of the function $f(\mathbf{a}_n)$. Further, it exhibits that the error in Monte Carlo integration scales like $1/\sqrt{N}$ which is independent of the dimension n . In practice, we estimate true variance σ by sample variance S , which is computed as follows:

$$S^2 = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{k=1}^N (f(\mathbf{a}_n^k) - E)^2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N (f(\mathbf{a}_n^k))^2 - E^2. \quad (8)$$

The main advantages of the Monte Carlo lie in the fact that the error estimate does not depend on the dimension n or integral fold n . However, the Monte Carlo estimate converges slowly to the true value at the rate of $\frac{1}{\sqrt{N}}$.⁴⁶ The ordinary or crude Monte Carlo simulation works pretty well for many aggregation operators. Further, one can make the estimation of performance measures in crude Monte Carlo more efficient by using known information about the behaviour of the aggregation operators. In principle, the behavioural information about the integrand allows us to reduce the variance of the estimate.⁴⁶ For this purpose, many variance reduction techniques have been proposed in the literature, such as, antithetic random variables, control variables, conditional Monte Carlo, Stratification, Latin hypercube sampling, importance sampling, quasi-Monte Carlo and splitting approach.⁴⁷⁻⁵⁰ The choice of the method for reduction of variance particularly derived from the behaviour of the integrand.^{46,50} For example, stratified sampling is useful when the variation of the integrand concentrate in a small region of the integration volume. Sometimes the choice is derived by the trade-off between complexity of variance reduction technique and improvement over crude Monte Carlo.^{46,49,50}

In this study, in most of the evaluation cases, we use Monte Carlo or *quasi*-Monte Carlo to find the estimate of the n -fold integral. Here, we provide the comparison of performance of Monte Carlo and *quasi*-Monte Carlo for the $orness(GM(\mathbf{a}_5))$ in terms of empirical standard deviation. For given N , we take 50 samples of the estimate of $orness(GM(\mathbf{a}_5))$ by using Monte Carlo and *quasi*-Monte Carlo and compute the empirical standard deviation in both cases. We use Faure sequences⁵¹ to generate pseudo random points in the *quasi*-Monte Carlo implementation. The results are presented in Fig. 2. We have used log – log plot to show the slopes and deviation between the Monte Carlo and *quasi*-Monte Carlo. Clearly, *quasi*-Monte Carlo provides better estimate than Monte Carlo.

Figure 2: Comparison of empirical standard deviation estimates of $orness(GM(\mathbf{a}_5))$

3. Orness of BM and its variants

In this section, we represent a framework for investigating the orness measure of BM and its variants. We start by recalling the definition of BM.

3.1. Orness measure of BM

Although, Bonferroni mean was introduced by Bonferroni⁵² in 1950, it is analyzed and interpreted in decision making context by Yager.⁵³ Bonferroni mean is defined as follows:

Definition 4. Let p and $q \geq 0$, $p + q > 0$. For an input vector $\mathbf{a}_n = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) \in [0, 1]^n$, the Bonferroni mean can be defined as a mapping $BM : [0, 1]^n \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and given by

$$BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q) = \left(\frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n a_i^p a_j^q \right)^{\frac{1}{p+q}} \quad (9)$$

According to the Eq. (1), the orness measure of BM is given by

$$orness(BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)) = \frac{\int_{[0,1]^n} BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q) - \int_{[0,1]^n} \min(\mathbf{a}_n)}{\int_{[0,1]^n} \max(\mathbf{a}_n) - \int_{[0,1]^n} \min(\mathbf{a}_n)} \quad (10)$$

It is evident from Eq. (10) that for an input set of length n , the orness measure of the BM depends on its associated parameters p and q . With the different values of the parameters (p, q) , a decision maker may achieve different levels of orness according to the context of decision making scenario and attitude towards the aggregation process. Therefore, the parameters p and q provides a decision maker the flexibility of modelling his/her attitude towards aggregation process in a more comprehend way.

Further, from Eq. (10), we note that the nature of orness measure of BM completely depends on the behaviour of the $BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)$ with respect to the associated parameters p and q . For example, if $BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)$ is increasing

with respect to p when q is fixed, then $orness(BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q))$ also exhibits the similar behaviour with respect to p . Thus, to determine the behaviour of the $orness(BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q))$ with respect to p and q , it is sufficient to investigate the nature of $BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)$ with respect to the parameters p and q . In light of this fact, we investigate the behaviour of BM and its variants with respect to the parameters p and q .

Proposition 1. $BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)$ is increasing with respect to p under the condition $p > q$, i.e.,

$$BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p_1, q) \geq BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p_2, q) \quad (11)$$

where $p_1 > p_2$ and $p_1, p_2 > q$.

Proof. Taking logarithm with base e to the both sides of Eq. (9) and differentiating partially with respect to p , we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)} \frac{\partial BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)}{\partial p} \\ = & \frac{1}{BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)} \left[-\frac{1}{(p+q)^2} \ln \left(\frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n a_i^p a_j^q \right) + \frac{1}{(p+q) \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n a_i^p a_j^q} \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n a_i^p a_j^q \ln a_i \right] \\ \geq & \frac{1}{BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)} \left[-\frac{1}{(p+q)^2 n(n-1)} \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n \ln(a_i^p a_j^q) + \frac{1}{(p+q) \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n a_i^p a_j^q} \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n a_i^p a_j^q \ln a_i \right] \\ = & \frac{1}{BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)} \left[\frac{(p+q)n(n-1) \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n a_i^p a_j^q \ln a_i - \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n a_i^p a_j^q \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n \ln(a_i^p a_j^q)}{(p+q)^2 n(n-1) \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n a_i^p a_j^q} \right] \\ = & \frac{1}{BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)} \left[\frac{\sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n a_i^p a_j^q (n(n-1)(p+q) \ln a_i - \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n \ln(a_i^p a_j^q))}{(p+q)^2 n(n-1) \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n a_i^p a_j^q} \right] \\ = & \frac{1}{BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)} \left[\frac{\sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n a_i^p a_j^q (n(n-1)(p+q) \ln a_i - (p+q)(n-1) \sum_{i=1}^n \ln a_i)}{(p+q)^2 n(n-1) \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n a_i^p a_j^q} \right] \\ = & \frac{1}{BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)} \left[\frac{(n-1)(p+q) \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n a_i^p a_j^q (\ln a_i - \ln \prod_{k=1, k \neq i}^n a_k)}{(p+q)^2 n(n-1) \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n a_i^p a_j^q} \right] \\ = & \frac{1}{BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)} \left[\frac{(n-1)(p+q) \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ j > i}}^n a_i^p a_j^q \left(\ln \frac{a_i}{\prod_{k=1, k \neq i}^n a_k} \right) + a_j^p a_i^q \left(\ln \frac{a_j}{\prod_{k=1, k \neq j}^n a_k} \right)}{(p+q)^2 n(n-1) \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n a_i^p a_j^q} \right] \\ = & \frac{1}{BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)} \left[\frac{(n-1)(p+q) \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ j > i}}^n a_i^p a_j^q \left(\ln \frac{a_i}{a_j} \right) + a_j^p a_i^q \left(\ln \frac{a_i}{a_j} \right) + (n-1)(p+q) \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n a_i^p a_j^q \ln \left(\frac{1}{\prod_{k=1, k \neq i, j}^n a_k} \right)}{(p+q)^2 n(n-1) \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n a_i^p a_j^q} \right] \\ = & \frac{1}{BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)} \left[\frac{(n-1)(p+q) \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ j > i}}^n a_i^p a_j^q \left(\ln \frac{a_i}{a_j} \right) [1 - \left(\frac{a_j}{a_i} \right)^{p-q}] + (n-1)(p+q) \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n a_i^p a_j^q \ln \left(\frac{1}{\prod_{k=1, k \neq i, j}^n a_k} \right)}{(p+q)^2 n(n-1) \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n a_i^p a_j^q} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

From Eq. (12), it is clear that the numerator will be positive when $\ln\left(\frac{a_i}{a_j}\right)[1 - \left(\frac{a_j}{a_i}\right)^{p-q}]$ is positive for all admissible pairs of i, j . We note that when $p > q$, $\ln\left(\frac{a_i}{a_j}\right)[1 - \left(\frac{a_j}{a_i}\right)^{p-q}] \geq 0$ for all i, j . Therefore, $\frac{\partial BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)}{\partial p} \geq 0$. Hence the results. \square

Proposition 2. $BM(a_n, p, p)$ is increasing with respect to the parameter p .

Proof. When $p = q$, from Eq. (9) we obtain

$$BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, p) = \left(\frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n (a_i a_j)^p \right)^{\frac{1}{2p}} \quad (13)$$

Taking logarithm with base e to the both sides of Eq. (13) and differentiating with respect to p , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, p)} \frac{dBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, p)}{dp} \\ = & \frac{1}{BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, p)} \left[-\frac{1}{4p^2} \ln \left(\frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n (a_i a_j)^p \right) + \frac{1}{(2p) \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n (a_i a_j)^p} \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n (a_i a_j)^p \ln(a_i a_j) \right] \\ \geq & \frac{1}{BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, p)} \left[-\frac{1}{4p^2} \left(\frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n \ln(a_i a_j)^p \right) + \frac{1}{(2p) \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n (a_i a_j)^p} \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n (a_i a_j)^p \ln(a_i a_j) \right] \\ = & \frac{1}{BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, p)} \left[\frac{(n-1) \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n (a_i a_j)^p \ln \left(\frac{a_i a_j}{\prod_{k_1 \neq i, k_2 \neq j} a_{k_1} a_{k_2}} \right)}{2pn(n-1) \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n (a_i a_j)^p} \right] \\ \geq & 0 \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Hence the results. \square

Remark 1. Further, we can note that when limit of p tends to 0 from positive side, $BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, p)$ exactly same as GM of the input set \mathbf{a}_n i.e., $\lim_{p \rightarrow 0^+} BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, p) = (\prod_{i=1}^n a_i)^{1/n} = GM(\mathbf{a}_n)$.

Since the function $BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)$ is symmetric with respect to the parameters p and q , the following proposition holds.

Proposition 3. $BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)$ is increasing with respect with respect to q under the condition $q > p$, i.e.,

$$BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q_1) \geq BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q_2) \quad (15)$$

where $q_1 > q_2$ and $q_1, q_2 > p$.

Proof. The proof of Proposition 3 can be easily completed in the lines of Proposition 1. \square

When we fix the parameters, the orness of BM typically depends on the length of the input vector n and their dependency relation can be expressed in the form of the following proposition.

Proposition 4. For fixed values of the parameters p and q , orness measure of $BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)$ operator is increasing with respect to the length of the input vector n , i.e.,

$$orness(BM(\mathbf{a}_{n_1}, p, q)) \leq orness(BM(\mathbf{a}_{n_2}, p, q)), \text{ when } n_1 \leq n_2 \quad (16)$$

Consider the $BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)$ with the parameters $(3, 1)$. When length of the input vector varies from 2 to 30, the results of orness levels has been depicted in the Fig. 3. We further note that when n varies over 2 to 10 there is a sharp increase in the orness levels.

Figure 3: Orness levels of $BM(\mathbf{a}_n, 3, 1)$

3.2. Orness measure of GBM

Based on GM and BM, Xia et al.⁵⁴ proposed another version of BM, which is known as GBM. It can be defined as follows:

Definition 5.⁵⁴ Let $\mathbf{a}_n = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)$, $n \geq 2$ be a collection of non-negative real values. Assume $p, q \geq 0$ with $p + q > 0$. The GBM of the collection (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) is defined as:

$$GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q) = \frac{1}{p + q} \prod_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n (pa_i + qa_j)^{\frac{1}{n(n-1)}}. \quad (17)$$

One may observe that the proper application of GBM requires two parameters p and q . For appropriate choice of these parameters, we need to analyse the behaviour of GBM with respect to these parameters. In the following, we describe the nature of the GBM with respect to the parameters p and q , and its connections with other aggregation operators.

Proposition 5. For any fixed input \mathbf{a}_n , $GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)$ is weakly monotone with respect to the parameters p and q , i.e.,

$$GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p + \delta, q + \delta) \geq GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q) \quad (18)$$

where $\delta \in \mathbb{R}$ such that $p + \delta > 0$ and $q + \delta > 0$

Proof. To prove this, we utilize the fact that the weak monotonicity⁵⁵ is equivalent to the non-negativity of the directional derivative $D_1GBM(\mathbf{a}, p, q) \geq 0$. For that purpose, we first differentiate Eq. (17) with respect to p partially

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)}{\partial p} &= \prod_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n \left(\frac{pa_i + qa_j}{p+q} \right)^{\frac{1}{n(n-1)}-1} \frac{(p+q)a_i - (a_i p + a_j q)}{(p+q)^2} \\
&= GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q) \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n \frac{q(a_i - a_j)}{(p+q)n(n-1)(a_i p + a_j q)} \\
&= GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q) \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i < j}}^n \frac{-(a_i - a_j)^2(p-q)q}{(p+q)n(n-1)(a_i p + a_j q)(pa_j + qa_i)} \tag{19}
\end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we obtain

$$\frac{\partial GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)}{\partial q} = GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q) \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i < j}}^n \frac{(a_j - a_i)^2(p-q)p}{(p+q)n(n-1)(a_i p + a_j q)(pa_j + qa_i)} \tag{20}$$

With the help of Eqs. (19) and (20), we find the directional derivative of $GBM(\mathbf{a}, p, q)$ in the direction $(1, 1)$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
D_1GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q) &= \left(\frac{\partial GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)}{\partial p}, \frac{\partial GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)}{\partial q} \right) \cdot (1, 1) \\
&= \frac{\partial GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)}{\partial p} + \frac{\partial GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)}{\partial q} \\
&= GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q) \sum_{\substack{i \notin I' \\ j \in I_i \\ j > i}} \frac{(a_i - a_j)^2(p-q)^2}{(p+q)(pa_i + qa_j)(pa_j + qa_i)n(n-1)} \\
&\geq 0
\end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. □

Remark 2. From Eq. (19), one may note that when $p < q$, $\frac{\partial GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)}{\partial p} \geq 0$. That is for any fixed $\mathbf{a}_n \in [0, 1]^n$, $GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p_1, q) \leq GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p_2, q)$ when $p_1 \leq p_2$ and $p_1, p_2 > q$. As $GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)$ is symmetric with respect to the parameters p and q , the condition reverse when p is fixed and that is evident from the Eq. (20).

In our next result, we establish the link between GBM and GM.

Proposition 6. For any fixed $\mathbf{a}_n \in [0, 1]^n$, ($n \geq 2$) and $p, q \geq 0$ with $p + q > 0$, we have

$$GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q) \geq \frac{p}{p+q} GM(\mathbf{a}_n) \tag{21}$$

The equality occurs when $\mathbf{a}_n = (a, a, \dots, a)$ or $\mathbf{a}_n = (a_1, \dots, 0, \dots, 0, \dots, a_n)$.

Proof. First we note that Eq. (17) can be put into the following form:

$$GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q) = \frac{1}{p+q} \prod_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n (pa_i + qa_j)^{\frac{1}{n(n-1)}} = \prod_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n \left(\frac{pa_i + qa_j}{p+q} \right)^{\frac{1}{n(n-1)}}.$$

As $a_i \in [0, 1]$ for all $i = 1, \dots, n$ and $p, q > 0$, we have $\frac{pa_i + qa_j}{p+q} \geq \frac{p}{p+q} a_i$ for all $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$. This implies that

$$\prod_{\substack{j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n \frac{pa_i + qa_j}{p+q} \geq \left(\frac{p}{p+q} \right)^{n(n-1)} \prod_{i=1}^n a_i^{n-1} \text{ for all } i = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (22)$$

It follows that

$$\prod_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n \left(\frac{pa_i + qa_j}{p+q} \right)^{\frac{1}{n(n-1)}} \geq \left(\left(\frac{p}{p+q} \right)^{n(n-1)} \prod_{i=1}^n a_i^{n-1} \right)^{\frac{1}{n(n-1)}} \quad (23)$$

Hence the results. \square

Remark 3. From the inequality (Eq. (21)) in Proposition 6, it is evident that when $p = q$, $GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, p) \geq \frac{1}{2}GM(\mathbf{a}_n)$. Therefore, when $p = q$, the behaviour property of GBM does not depend on the parameters. In fact it is only depends on the length of the input vectors.

Remark 4. As $GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)$ is symmetric with respect to the parameters p and q , from Eq. (21), we further obtain

$$GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q) \geq \frac{q}{p+q} GM(\mathbf{a}_n) \quad (24)$$

Moreover, one may infer from Eqs. (21) and (24) that

$$GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q) \geq \min \left(\frac{q}{p+q}, \frac{p}{p+q} \right) GM(\mathbf{a}_n). \quad (25)$$

Further, from the perspective of the Proposition 6, we can derive lower bound for the orness measure of GBM with the help of orness measure of GM.

Proposition 7. For any $p, q > 0$, the orness measure of the GBM satisfies the following condition:

$$orness(GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)) \geq \frac{p}{p+q} \left(\frac{n}{n+1} \right)^{n-1} \frac{n}{n-1} - \frac{1}{n-1} \quad (26)$$

Proof. From the definition of the orness, we have

$$orness(GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)) = \frac{\int_{[0,1]^n} GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q) - \int_{[0,1]^n} \min(\mathbf{a}_n)}{\int_{[0,1]^n} \max(\mathbf{a}_n) - \int_{[0,1]^n} \min(\mathbf{a}_n)} \quad (27)$$

Since the Proposition 6 holds for every $\mathbf{a}_n \in [0, 1]^n$ and $p, q > 0$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
orness(GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)) &\geq \frac{\int_{[0,1]^n} \frac{p}{p+q} GM(\mathbf{a}_n) - \int_{[0,1]^n} \min(\mathbf{a}_n)}{\int_{[0,1]^n} \max(\mathbf{a}_n) - \int_{[0,1]^n} \min(\mathbf{a}_n)} \\
&\geq \frac{\frac{p}{p+q} \left(\frac{n}{n+1} \right)^n - \frac{1}{n+1}}{\frac{n}{n+1} - \frac{1}{n+1}} \\
&= \frac{p}{p+q} \left(\frac{n}{n+1} \right)^{n-1} \frac{n}{n-1} - \frac{1}{n-1}
\end{aligned} \tag{28}$$

□

Remark 5. From Eq. (26), it is clear that bound of the GBM directly depends on the parameters (p, q) . Further, when one parameter increases indefinitely and other remains fixed, the values of the bound getting closer to the orness of the GM. Moreover, when one parameter tends to ∞ and other remain fixed, $\max(\frac{p}{p+q}, \frac{q}{p+q}) \rightarrow 1$ and therefore, $orness(GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)) \rightarrow (\frac{n}{n+1})^{n-1} \frac{n}{n-1} - \frac{1}{n-1}$, which is orness of the GM. This behaviour of the orness of GBM and its bound has been depicted in the Fig. 4. It is to be noted that, we set $q = 1$ when p varies 2 to 100. For each set of values of (p, q) , orness is computed by Monte Carlo algorithm.

Figure 4: Behaviour of orness levels of $GBM(\mathbf{a}_4, p, 1)$ and its' bounds

Proposition 8. For fixed values of the parameters (p, q) , orness measure of GBM depends on the length of input vector $\mathbf{a}_n \in [0, 1]^n$ and satisfies the following condition:

$$orness(GBM(\mathbf{a}_{n_1}, p, q)) \geq orness(GBM(\mathbf{a}_{n_2}, p, q)) \text{ whenever } n_1 < n_2 \tag{29}$$

For fixed values of the parameters $(p, q) = (1, 2)$, we compute the orness measures of $GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)$ for different length of the input vectors n by using Monte Carlo and the results are depicted in the Fig. 5.

3.3. Orness measure of PBM

PBM is another variants of BM, which is capable of capturing partition structure interrelationship pattern among the input set in the aggregation process and reflects it in the aggregated value.⁵⁶ In the following, we provide the

Figure 5: Orness levels of $GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, 2, 1)$

brief description of the specific partition structure interrelationship pattern and PBM operator.

Let $\mathbf{a}_n = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)$ be the collection of inputs, with a_i 's being non-negative real numbers. Suppose, on the basis of the inter-relationship pattern, the input set \mathbf{a}_n is partitioned into d distinct classes P_1, P_2, \dots, P_d such that $P_i \cap P_j = \phi$ for all $i \neq j$, $i, j \in \{1, 2, \dots, d\}$, $\cup_{r=1}^d P_r = \mathbf{a}_n$ and $|P_i| \geq 2$ for all $i = 1, 2, \dots, d$. We further assume that the inputs of each P_i are interrelated and there is no inter-relationship among the data of any two partitions P_i and P_j whenever $i, j \in \{1, 2, \dots, d\}$ and $i \neq j$. With these assumptions and notations, the PBM operator of the collection of inputs (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) is defined as follows:

Definition 6. ⁵⁶ For $p, q \geq 0$ with $p + q > 0$, the PBM operator is a mapping $PBM : [0, 1]^n \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that

$$PBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q) = \frac{1}{d} \left(\sum_{r=1}^d \left(\frac{1}{|P_r|} \sum_{i \in P_r} a_i^p \left(\frac{1}{|P_r| - 1} \sum_{\substack{j \neq i \\ j \in P_r}} a_j^q \right) \right)^{\frac{1}{p+q}} \right) \quad (30)$$

where $|P_r|$ = cardinality of P_r .

We can re-write Eq. (30) in more compact form with the help of Eq. (9) as follows:

$$PBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q) = \frac{1}{d} \sum_{r=1}^d BM(\mathbf{a}_{P_r}, p, q) \quad (31)$$

where $\mathbf{a}_{P_r} = (a_i)_{i \in P_r}$.

From Definition 6, it is evident that PBM involves two parameters p and q . It is important to analyse the behaviour of the PBM with respect to these parameters. In this following proposition, we state the nature of PBM with respect to the parameters p and q .

Proposition 9. For any fixed partition $P = \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_d\}$ of the input set \mathbf{a}_n , the aggregation operator $PBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)$ is increasing with respect to p under the condition $p > q$, i.e.,

$$PBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p_1, q) \geq PBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p_2, q) \quad (32)$$

where $p_1 > p_2$ and $p_1, p_2 > q$.

The connection between orness measures of PBM and BM aggregation operators can be characterized in the following proposition.

Proposition 10. For any fixed partition $P = \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_d\}$ of the input set \mathbf{a}_n ,

$$\text{orness}(PBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)) = \frac{1}{d} \sum_{d=1}^r \text{orness}(BM(\mathbf{a}_{P_r}, p, q)) \quad (33)$$

where $p, q > 0$ and $p + q > 0$.

Proof. The proof of the theorem follows from the Eq. (1) directly. \square

Remark 6. Further, from Proposition 10, one can easily infer the bounds of the orness measure of PBM. For the fixed values of the parameters p and q , the orness measure satisfies the following inequalities:

$$\text{orness}(BM(\mathbf{a}_{P_{\min}}, p, q)) \leq \text{orness}(PBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)) \leq \text{orness}(BM(\mathbf{a}_{P_{\max}}, p, q)) \quad (34)$$

where $P_{\max} = \max_r |P_r|$ and $P_{\min} = \min_r |P_r|$.

It is evident that orness of the PBM for a fixed length of the input vector not only depends on the parameters p and q but also depends on the structure of the partition of the inputs. Different partition structures may yield different levels of orness for a fixed values of the parameters (p, q) . Note that for a fixed length input vector, say n , there are $B(n)$ partitions of the input set, where $B(n)$ is the *Bell number*⁵⁷. One may compute the *Bell number* by using following recursion rule:

$$B(n+1) = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} B(k) \quad (35)$$

with the following conditions $B(0) = 1$ and $B(1) = 1$. Further, from the definition of PBM, we observe that the cardinality of each member of a partition should be greater than or equal to 2. Therefore, for an input set with length n , we are looking for the partitions, which does not contain any singleton set. Clearly, this kind of partitions will follow interrelationship pattern of PBM. Let $B^*(n)$ be the number of partitions of a set with n elements which do not contain any singleton set. Then, we can observe the relation between $B(n)$ and $B^*(n)$ in Table I. From the Table I, it is clear that $B^*(n+1) = B(n) - B^*(n)$. Therefore, for an input set of length n , $B^*(n+1) = B(n) - B^*(n)$ different partitioned structure Bonferroni mean (PBM) possible. Different structure partitions may produce different aggregation results and their orness values vary across the partitions at certain levels.

Example 1. Let us consider the input of length 4 from the unit hypercube $[0, 1]^n$. According to the *Bell number*, there are $B(4) = 15$ possible partitions of the input set. Among them, only 4 satisfy the structure of the PBM

No. of arguments (n)	No. of Partitions ($B(n)$)	No. of partitions with PBM structure
3	5	1
4	15	4
5	52	11
6	203	41

interrelationship patterns. In Table II, we describe the partitions with corresponding orness measure of PBM operators for the fixed value of the parameters $(p, q) = (1, 2)$. Further, we note from Table II that orness levels for the partitions $P_1 - P_3$ are same even though the partitions are distinct.

Table II: Orness under different partition structures

No. (P_r)	Partition	Orness
P_1	$\{\{1, 2\}, \{3, 4\}\}$	0.4330
P_2	$\{\{1, 3\}, \{2, 4\}\}$	0.4330
P_3	$\{\{1, 4\}, \{2, 3\}\}$	0.4330
P_4	$\{1, 2, 3, 4\}$	0.5209

It has been observed from the Example 1, that partitions $P_1 - P_3$ have equal numbers of subsets and cardinality of the subsets are equal. This fact can be generalized in the following way.

Definition 7. Let $P = \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_r\}$ be the partitions of a input set with n elements. We are going to define cardinality set of the partition P as follows:

$$|P| = \{|P_i| : P_i \in P\} \quad (36)$$

where $|A|$ denotes the cardinality of the set A .

Definition 8. Let $P = \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_r\}$ and $Q = \{Q_1, Q_2, \dots, Q_r\}$ be the two partitions of an input set of length n . We say P and Q are cardinality equivalent if $|P| = |Q|$.

Example 2. Let $P = \{\{a_1, a_3\}, \{a_2, a_4, a_5\}\}$ and $Q = \{\{a_2, a_3, a_5\}, \{a_1, a_4\}\}$ be the two partitions over the input $\mathbf{a}_5 = (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5)$. According to the Definition 7, the cardinality sets of the partitions P and Q are $|P| = \{2, 3\}$ and $|Q| = \{3, 2\}$, respectively. Therefore, $|P|$ and $|Q|$ are cardinality equivalent partitions of the input set \mathbf{a}_5 .

Proposition 11. Let $P = \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_r\}$ and $Q = \{Q_1, Q_2, \dots, Q_r\}$ be the two cardinality equivalent partitions of an input set of length n . Then for a fixed values of the parameters (p, q)

$$orness(PBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q, P)) = orness(PBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q, Q)) \quad (37)$$

Here, we use the notation $PBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q, P)$ in place of original notation $PBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)$ to emphasize the dependency on partition.

Proof. From Eq. (31), we have

$$\text{orness}(PBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q, P)) = \frac{1}{d} \sum_{r=1}^d \text{orness}(BM(\mathbf{a}_{P_d}, p, q)) \quad (38)$$

and

$$\text{orness}(PBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q, Q)) = \frac{1}{d} \sum_{r=1}^d \text{orness}(BM(\mathbf{a}_{Q_d}, p, q)) \quad (39)$$

As P and Q are cardinality equivalent partition, for any $P_d \in P$ there exists a $Q_k \in Q$ such that $|P_d| = |Q_k|$ and that implies

$$\text{orness}(BM(\mathbf{a}_{Q_k}, p, q)) = \text{orness}(BM(\mathbf{a}_{P_d}, p, q)). \quad (40)$$

One may note that the Eq. (40) is true for any partition $P_d \in P$ under cardinality equivalent partitions. Hence it follows the Eq. (37). \square

4. Estimation of parameters from orness measure

Now, we are going to denote the domain of the parameters p and q as D_{pq} and it is defined as $D_{pq} = \{(p, q) \in \mathbb{R}^2 : p, q \geq 0, p + q > 0\}$. Further, we denote the set of all pairs (p, q) from D_{pq} such that $p > q$ as $D_{p>q}$, i.e. $D_{p>q} = \{(p, q) \in D_{pq} : p > q\}$.

The usual lexicographic ordering between the elements (p_1, q_1) and (p_2, q_2) of D_{pq} is defined as follows: $(p_1, q_1) \leq_2 (p_2, q_2)$ when $p_1 \leq p_2 \cap q_1 \leq q_2$. Note that D_{pq} equipped with the ordering \leq_2 is a lattice.

Proposition 12. For any (p_1, q_1) and (p_2, q_2) from $D_{p>q}$, the BM operator satisfies

$$BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p_1, q_1) \leq BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p_2, q_2) \quad \text{whenever } (p_1, q_1) \leq_2 (p_2, q_2) \quad (41)$$

Let L be the line joining the points $a = (p_1, q_1)$ and $b = (p_2, q_2)$, i.e. $L = \{a\lambda + (1 - \lambda)b : \lambda \in [0, 1]\}$. From Proposition 9, it is clear that BM is increasing along the the line L . Further, for any point $c \in L$, we have $BM(\mathbf{a}_n, a) \leq BM(\mathbf{a}_n, c) \leq BM(\mathbf{a}_n, b)$. As $BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)$ is continuous with respect to p and q , it takes every values from the interval $[BM(\mathbf{a}_n, a), BM(\mathbf{a}_n, b)]$ (by intermediate value property of the continuous function).

Example 3. Let $\mathbf{a}_4 = (0.3, 0.7, 0.2, 0.5)$ be the fixed input vector from unit hypercube $[0, 1]^4$. Consider two points $a = (2, 1)$ and $b = (8, 9)$ from $D_{p>q}$. The monotone behaviour of $BM(\mathbf{a}_4, p, q)$ along the line segment L joining the points a and b is depicted in the Fig. 6. It has been observed that, $BM(\mathbf{a}_4, p, q)$ is increasing in the direction a to b .

We have seen that orness of the BM typically depends on the parameters p and q and length of the input vectors. One of the typical question associated with the orness measure of BM is how one can obtain the value

Figure 6: Behaviour of $BM(a_4, p, q)$ along the line L joining the points $(2, 1)$ and $(9, 8)$

of the parameters p and q for a given value of the orness and fixed length of the input vector. In other words, we are interested to solve the following equation:

$$\alpha = \frac{\int_{[0,1]^n} BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q) - \int_{[0,1]^n} \min(\mathbf{x})}{\int_{[0,1]^n} \max(\mathbf{x}) - \int_{[0,1]^n} \min(\mathbf{x})} = \frac{\int_{[0,1]^n} BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q) - \frac{1}{n+1}}{\frac{n}{n+1} - \frac{1}{n+1}} \quad (42)$$

As the determination of closed form of n -fold integral associated with $BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)$ is quite impossible, it is very difficult to find the solution of the Eq. (42). However, we can find an estimate of the n -fold integral for a given pairs of the parameters (p, q) by using Monte Carlo simulation method. Let $E(BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q))$ be the Monte Carlo estimate of the n -fold integral $\int_{[0,1]^n} BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)$. By taking number of sample in the domain of the integration large enough, it is possible to get close approximation of $\int_{[0,1]^n} BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)$. With the estimated value $E(BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q))$, the Eq. (42) can be re-written as follows:

$$\frac{n+1}{n-1} E(BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)) - \frac{1}{n-1} - \alpha = 0 \quad (43)$$

Thus, our problem of finding the values of the parameters boils down into a root finding problem of the following equation:

$$R(p, q) = \frac{n+1}{n-1} E(BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)) - \frac{1}{n-1} - \alpha = 0 \quad (44)$$

In aim of solving the above Eq. (44), we are going to exploit the behavioural property of the orness measure of BM over the domain of the parameters $D_{p>q}$. In particular, we will use the monotonic behaviour of $E(BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q))$ in the domain of the parameters $D_{p>q}$.

Proposition 13. For any (p_1, q_1) and (p_2, q_2) from $D_{p>q}$, the Monte Carlo estimate $E(BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q))$ of the

n -fold integral involving BM, $\int_{[0,1]^n} BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)$ satisfies

$$E(BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p_1, q_1)) \leq E(BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p_2, q_2)) \quad \text{whenever } (p_1, q_1) \leq_2 (p_2, q_2) \quad (45)$$

Proof. For the k -th sample point $\mathbf{a}_n^k \in [0, 1]^n$, we have

$$BM(\mathbf{a}_n^k, p_1, q_1) \leq BM(\mathbf{a}_n^k, p_2, q_2) \quad \text{whenever } (p_1, q_1) \leq_2 (p_2, q_2) \text{ and } (p_1, q_1), (p_2, q_2) \in D_{p>q}. \quad (46)$$

Let N be the number of sampling points from $[0, 1]^n$, which are used to compute $E(BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q))$. Evidently, the inequality Eq. (46) is valid for all the sample points $\mathbf{a}_n^k \in [0, 1]^n$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, N$. Summing up over all the inequalities, we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^N BM(\mathbf{a}_n^k, p_1, q_1) \leq \sum_{k=1}^N BM(\mathbf{a}_n^k, p_2, q_2) \quad \text{whenever } (p_1, q_1) \leq_2 (p_2, q_2) \text{ and } (p_1, q_1), (p_2, q_2) \in D_{p>q}. \quad (47)$$

It follows that

$$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N BM(\mathbf{a}_n^k, p_1, q_1) \leq \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N BM(\mathbf{a}_n^k, p_2, q_2) \quad \text{whenever } (p_1, q_1) \leq_2 (p_2, q_2) \text{ and } (p_1, q_1), (p_2, q_2) \in D_{p>q}. \quad (48)$$

Hence, the result. □

Remark 7. As a consequence of the result of Proposition 13, we can say the estimated value of the integral $E(BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q))$ exhibits the monotone behaviour along the line L and satisfies the relation $E(BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p_1, q_1)) \leq E(BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)) \leq E(BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p_2, q_2))$ where $(p, q) \in L$. Further, for different values of $(p, q) \in L$, the estimate $E(BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q))$ takes values from the closed interval $[E(BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p_1, q_1)), E(BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p_2, q_2))]$. This behaviour of the Monte Carlo estimate, $E(BM(\mathbf{a}_5, p, q))$ of the integral $\int_{[0,1]^n} BM(\mathbf{a}_5, p, q)$ along the line L joining the points (3, 2) and (8, 7) has been depicted in the Fig. 7.

In the next, we describe the behaviour of the Monte Carlo estimates of the n -fold integrals of GBM and PBM.

Proposition 14. For any two points (p_1, q_1) and (p_2, q_2) from $D_{p,q}$, the Monte Carlo estimate $E(GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q))$ of the n -fold integral involving $\int_{[0,1]^n} GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q)$ satisfies

$$E(GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p_1, q_1)) \leq E(GBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p_2, q_2)) \quad \text{whenever } (p_2, q_2) = (p_1, q_1) + a(1, 1), \quad a \in \mathcal{R}^+ \quad (49)$$

where \mathcal{R}^+ is the set of non-negative real numbers.

Proposition 15. For a fix partition structure of the input set \mathbf{a}_n, P and any (p_1, q_1) and (p_2, q_2) from $D_{p>q}$, the Monte Carlo estimate $E(PBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q, P))$ of the n -fold integral involving PBM, $\int_{[0,1]^n} PBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q, P)$

Figure 7: Behaviour of $E(BM(\mathbf{a}_5, p, q))$ along the line L joining the points $(3, 2)$ and $(8, 7)$

satisfies

$$E(PBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p_1, q_1, P)) \leq E(PBM(\mathbf{a}_n, p_2, q_2, P)) \quad \text{whenever } (p_1, q_1) \leq_2 (p_2, q_2) \quad (50)$$

Based on this monotone property of the estimate $E(BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q))$ along any line $L \subset D_{p>q}$ joining the end points $(p_1, q_1), (p_2, q_2) \in D_{p>q}$ with $(p_1, q_1) \leq_2 (p_2, q_2)$, we design an algorithm for finding the value of the parameters p and q which satisfies the Eq. (44). The algorithm is designed based on the principle of bisection method coupled with Monte Carlo simulation. In our algorithm Monte Carlo simulation is utilized to find the estimate $E(BM(\mathbf{a}_n, p, q))$ for a given value of the pairs (p, q) and the bisection method is employed to find the new estimate along the line L . Before the realization of the steps of the algorithm, we describe its initialization and working principles.

Let $a^{(1)} = (p_1, q_1)$ and $b^{(1)} = (p_2, q_2)$ are two points from the domain of the parameters $D_{p>q}$ such that $R(a^{(1)})R(b^{(1)}) < 0$. In other words $R(a^{(1)})$ and $R(b^{(1)})$ have opposite signs. The sign condition ensures that the estimate values of the (p, q) lies on the line segment joining the points $a^{(1)}$ and $b^{(1)}$. Note that in computing $R(a^{(1)})$, we need to find the value of the estimate $E(BM(\mathbf{a}_n, a^{(1)}))$ by utilizing Monte Carlo simulation. Let $c^{(1)}$ be the new estimate of the parameters (p, q) such that $c^{(1)} = \frac{1}{2}(a^{(1)} + b^{(1)})$. After computing estimate $E(BM(\mathbf{a}_n, c^{(1)}))$ by using Monte Carlo simulation, one can observe that either $R(a^{(1)})R(c^{(1)}) < 0$ or $R(b^{(1)})R(c^{(1)}) < 0$. If $R(a^{(1)})R(c^{(1)}) < 0$, then the solution of the Eq. (44) lies on the line segment joining the points $a^{(1)}$ and $c^{(1)}$. Otherwise, it lies in the line segment joining the points $b^{(1)}$ and $c^{(1)}$. We choose the endpoints of line segment, which satisfies the opposite signs condition and repeat the process of bisection as long as the termination condition is reached. Generally, the termination condition is set as the Euclidean distance between $b^{(n)}$ and $c^{(n)}$, say $dist(b^{(n)}, c^{(n)})$, below a predefined threshold $\epsilon > 0$, where $a^{(n)}$ and $b^{(n)}$ are the end points after $(n - 1)^{th}$

iterations and $c^{(n)}$ is the midpoint. We illustrate few steps of the method graphically as in Fig. 8. Further, the steps of algorithm are summarized in **Algorithm 1**.

Figure 8: Steps of the bisection method applied over starting points $a^{(1)}$ and $b^{(1)}$

Algorithm 1: Find the parameters (p, q) for a given orness level α and input dimension n

Input : orness level α , length of the input n

Output: the parameters (p, q)

- 1 **Step 1:** Find two points $a^{(1)}, b^{(1)} \in D_{p>q}$ at which $R(p, q)$ has different sign
 - 2 **Step 2:** Set $c^{(1)} = \frac{a^{(1)}+b^{(1)}}{2}$
 - 3 **Step 3:** Compute $R(c^{(1)})$
 - 4 **Step 4:** If $R(a^{(1)})R(c^{(1)}) < 0$ then Set $b^{(1)} = c^{(1)}$;
 - 5 Else $a_1 = c_1$;
 - 6 **Step 5:** If $dist(b^{(1)}, c^{(1)}) \leq \epsilon$ then $(p, q) = c^{(1)}$
 - 7 Else Goto Step 2
-

Although, we have illustrated the estimation of the parameters from the decision maker's perspective towards aggregation in the case of BM, one can extend it for other aggregation operators easily as long as they satisfy monotonic behaviour with respect to the involving parameters. Further, the simulation strategies to estimate the integral allow us to extend for any aggregation operator with complex structure in the sense that it is not possible to derive the close form of the multi-fold integral involving orness measure. For example, the power arithmetic mean exhibits the monotonic behaviour with respect to its parameter and also it is not possible to find the closed form of the n -fold integral in the measure of orness. Hence, we can use the **Algorithm 1** to find the parameters for a given level of orness.

5. Numerical experiment

In the following, we illustrate few decision making scenarios, where the decision makers require to set the parameters (p, q) associated with different variants of BM based on their subjective views towards the aggregation process. In each case, we utilize the proposed algorithm for finding the value of the parameters through Monte Carlo.

Example 4. Consider an aggregation process involving interrelated inputs, i.e., each input is related to the rest of the inputs. In this view, decision maker decides to use BM as a method of aggregation of input of length 4, $BM(\mathbf{a}_4, p, q)$. There are several choices of the parameters p and q , and choosing the appropriate one is crucial to produce reliable results. Therefore, decision maker is interested to use relevant subjective knowledge about the problem to find the appropriate values of the parameters. In practice, decision maker's subjective view towards aggregation can be expressed via the behavioural property of the aggregation operator, namely, orness and *andness*. A decision maker with a pessimistic view may prefer high *andness*, whereas a decision maker with an optimistic perspective may prefer high orness. Based on the context of the problem and relevant knowledge, the decision maker's view towards aggregation is expressed by the orness measure $\alpha = 0.6$. Now, we are going to exploit this behavioural information to find the associated parameters p and q . In a nutshell, we utilize the **Algorithm 1** to find the values of the parameters p and q . Owing to initialize the algorithm, we look for two points $a^{(1)}$ and $b^{(1)}$ from the space $D_{p>q}$ where $R(p, q)$ differs in sign. Note that at $a^{(1)} = (1, 2)$, we obtain $R(a^{(1)}) = -0.0792$ while at $b^{(1)} = (4, 9)$, $R(b^{(1)}) = 0.1160$. Therefore, the points $a^{(1)}$ and $b^{(1)}$ satisfy the sign condition $R(a^{(1)}) \cdot R(b^{(1)}) < 0$. In determining the value of $R(p, q)$, we have used Monte Carlo to estimate $E(BM(\mathbf{a}_4, p, q))$. Let $\epsilon = 0.001$ be the error threshold. The results of the bisection algorithm have been detailed in the Table III. We note from the Table III that after 13 steps, we have $dist(b^{(13)}, c^{(13)}) = 0.0009297 < \epsilon$

Table III: Iterations for finding the values of parameters (p, q) of $BM(\mathbf{a}_4, p, q)$

n	$a^{(n)}$	$b^{(n)}$	$c^{(n)}$	$dist(b^{(n)}, c^{(n)})$	$R(c^{(n)})$
1	(1.000000, 2.000000)	(4.000000, 9.000000)	(2.500000, 5.500000)	3.8078866	0.05557886
2	(1.000000, 2.000000)	(2.500000, 5.500000)	(1.750000, 3.750000)	1.9039433	0.00379788
3	(1.000000, 2.000000)	(1.750000, 3.750000)	(1.375000, 2.875000)	0.9519716	-0.03164433
4	(1.375000, 2.875000)	(1.750000, 3.750000)	(1.562500, 3.312500)	0.4759858	-0.01259992
5	(1.562500, 3.312500)	(1.750000, 3.750000)	(1.656250, 3.531250)	0.2379929	-0.00442714
6	(1.656250, 3.531250)	(1.750000, 3.750000)	(1.703125, 3.640625)	0.1189965	-0.00000203
7	(1.703125, 3.640625)	(1.750000, 3.750000)	(1.7265625, 3.6953125)	0.0594982	0.00194160
8	(1.703125, 3.640625)	(1.7265625, 3.6953125)	(1.7148438, 3.6679688)	0.0297491	0.00100661
9	(1.703125, 3.640625)	(1.7148438, 3.6679688)	(1.7089844, 3.6542969)	0.0148746	0.00047270
10	(1.703125, 3.640625)	(1.7089844, 3.6542969)	(1.7060547, 3.6474609)	0.0074373	0.00002242
11	(1.703125, 3.640625)	(1.7060547, 3.6474609)	(1.7045898, 3.6440430)	0.0037186	0.00029119
12	(1.703125, 3.640625)	(1.7045898, 3.6440430)	(1.7038574, 3.6423340)	0.0018593	-0.00028049
13	(1.7038574, 3.6423340)	(1.7045898, 3.6440430)	(1.7042236, 3.6431885)	0.0009297	-0.00001711
14	(1.7042236, 3.6431885)	(1.7045898, 3.6440430)	(1.70440673, 3.6436157)	0.0004648	-0.00042786
15	(1.7044067, 3.6436157)	(1.7045898, 3.6440430)	(1.7044983, 3.6438293)	0.0002324	0.00007597

hence the required root approximation is $c^{(13)} = (1.7042236, 3.6431885)$. Further, by computing orness measure

of $BM(\mathbf{a}_4, p, q)$ with the parameter values (1.7042236, 3.6431885) via Monte Carlo, we obtain 0.6001, which is correct upto 3-decimal places. By decreasing the threshold value ϵ , one may get more reliable approximation of the parameters. Moreover, we could say that our Monte Carlo simulation based algorithm for finding the values of the parameters produce reliable result.

Example 5. Consider the formation of group opinion from individual opinions, where the interrelationship among the group members follows a partitioned structure pattern, mentioned earlier. Let the group consists of five individuals $\{D_1, D_2, D_3, D_4, D_5\}$. The interrelationship pattern of the group can be described via the following partitioned structure pattern $P = \{\{D_1, D_2\}, \{D_3, D_4, D_5\}\}$. Based on the interrelationship pattern, to form the group opinion by aggregating individual opinion, one can utilize $PBM(\mathbf{a}_5, p, q)$ as it has the capability to capture such interrelationship pattern in the aggregation process. But, we require a reasonable choice for the values of the parameters (p, q) . For reasonable choice of the parameters, we require additional information about the aggregation process. The additional information could in the form subjective view towards the aggregation process. Here, it may be the subjective attitude of the whole group towards the aggregation. As we have mentioned earlier, such attitude towards the aggregation could be expressed in terms of the behavioural property of the aggregation operator, we assume group attitude towards the aggregation is expressed as a orness measure of $PBM(\mathbf{a}_5, p, q)$, say $\alpha = 0.4$. It indicates a bit of pessimistic view of the group towards the aggregation process. We exploit this behavioural information of the aggregation process to find the appropriate choice of the parameters (p, q) . In aim of this, we are going to use **Algorithm 1** of finding the estimate (p, q) . We have set the iteration termination threshold $\epsilon = 0.001$. The results of each iteration step is summarized in the Table IV. It has been observed from the Table IV that after 13 steps we reached at the desired threshold level, i.e. $dist(b^{(13)}, c^{(13)}) < 0.0006302$ and desired value of the parameters $(p, q) = (1.0056641, 0.4189087)$.

Table IV: Iterations for finding the values of parameters (p, q) of $PBM(\mathbf{a}_5, p, q)$

n	$a^{(n)}$	$b^{(n)}$	$c^{(n)}$	$dist(b^{(n)}, c^{(n)})$	$R(c^{(n)})$
1	(0.2000000, 0.1000000)	(5.0000000, 2.0000000)	(2.6000000, 1.0500000)	2.5811819	0.07350933
2	(0.2000000, 0.1000000)	(2.6000000, 1.0500000)	(1.4000000, 0.5750000)	1.2905909	0.02183701
3	(0.2000000, 0.1000000)	(1.4000000, 0.5750000)	(0.8000000, 0.3375000)	0.6452955	-0.01219606
4	(0.8000000, 0.3375000)	(1.4000000, 0.5750000)	(1.1000000, 0.4562500)	0.3226477	0.00476096
5	(0.8000000, 0.3375000)	(1.1000000, 0.4562500)	(0.9500000, 0.3968750)	0.1613239	-0.00297173
6	(0.9500000, 0.3968750)	(1.1000000, 0.4562500)	(1.0250000, 0.4265625)	0.0806619	0.00195428
7	(0.9500000, 0.3968750)	(1.0250000, 0.4265625)	(0.9875000, 0.4117188)	0.0403310	-0.00097432
8	(0.9875000, 0.4117188)	(1.0250000, 0.4265625)	(1.0062500, 0.4191406)	0.0201655	0.00010877
9	(0.9875000, 0.4117188)	(1.0062500, 0.4191406)	(0.9968750, 0.4154297)	0.0100827	-0.00042106
10	(0.9968750, 0.4154297)	(1.0062500, 0.4191406)	(1.0015625, 0.4172852)	0.0050414	-0.00028956
11	(1.0015625, 0.4172852)	(1.0062500, 0.4191406)	(1.0039063, 0.4182129)	0.0025207	-0.00072568
12	(1.0039063, 0.4182129)	(1.0062500, 0.4191406)	(1.0050781, 0.4186768)	0.0012603	0.00051847
13	(1.0050781, 0.4186768)	(1.0062500, 0.4191406)	(1.0056641, 0.4189087)	0.0006302	-0.00013721
14	(1.0050781, 0.4186768)	(1.0056641, 0.4189087)	(1.0053711, 0.4187927)	0.0003151	-0.00009421
15	(1.0053711, 0.4187927)	(1.0056641, 0.4189087)	(1.0055176, 0.4188507)	0.0001575	-0.00029199

Example 6. Let us consider the aggregation of interrelated inputs with a mandatory requirement that for a non-

zero score of the aggregation, the average score of each pair of inputs should be above zero. Further, the inputs are interrelated in the form that each input is related to the rest of the inputs. The above-mentioned aggregation process of interrelated inputs with mandatory requirement can be suitably modeled via GBM operators defined in Eq. (17). Clearly, GBM produces non-zero score when average scores $\frac{pa_i+qa_j}{p+q}$ of each pair of inputs (a_i, a_j) above zero. As the length of input set is six, we will employ $GBM(\mathbf{a}_6, p, q)$ to obtain the overall score. The computation $GBM(\mathbf{a}_6, p, q)$ requires the parameters p and q satisfying the conditions $p + q > 0$ with $p, q \geq 0$. In aim of making reasonable choice of the parameters, we exploit the decision maker's attitude or perceived view towards aggregation process, which in general expressed via the behavioural property of aggregation operator. We assume that decision maker's perceived view expressed through orness level and it is given as $\alpha = 0.42$. Now, we aim to implement the **Algorithm 1** to find the value of the parameters (p, q) . Based on the weak monotonicity property of the GBM operator, we identify the points $a^{(1)} = (15, 1)$ and $b^{(1)} = (27, 13)$ in which $R(a^{(1)})$ and $R(b^{(1)})$ have opposite sign. We set the termination condition $\epsilon = 0.0003$. The steps of the Algorithm 1 are summarized in Table V. From the Table V, we note that the value of the parameters at desired threshold level is $(p, q) = (17.76324463, 3.763244629)$. With this estimated values of the parameters, decision maker can use $GBM(\mathbf{a}_6, 17.76324463, 3.763244629)$ operator to fuse the inputs.

Table V: Iterations for finding the values of parameters (p, q) of $GBM(\mathbf{a}_6, p, q)$

n	$a^{(n)}$	$b^{(n)}$	$c^{(n)}$	$dist(b^{(n)}, c^{(n)})$	$R(c^{(n)})$
1	(15.0000000, 1.0000000)	(27.0000000, 13.0000000)	(21.0000000, 7.0000000)	8.4852814	0.01366726
2	(15.0000000, 1.0000000)	(21.0000000, 7.0000000)	(18.0000000, 4.0000000)	4.2426407	0.00119492
3	(15.0000000, 1.0000000)	(18.0000000, 4.0000000)	(16.5000000, 2.5000000)	2.1213203	-0.01023846
4	(16.5000000, 2.5000000)	(18.0000000, 4.0000000)	(17.2500000, 3.2500000)	1.0606602	-0.00338747
5	(17.2500000, 3.2500000)	(18.0000000, 4.0000000)	(17.6250000, 3.6250000)	0.5303301	-0.00050796
6	(17.6250000, 3.6250000)	(18.0000000, 4.0000000)	(17.8125000, 3.8125000)	0.2651650	0.00064927
7	(17.6250000, 3.6250000)	(17.8125000, 3.8125000)	(17.7187500, 3.7187500)	0.1325825	-0.00055106
8	(17.7187500, 3.7187500)	(17.8125000, 3.8125000)	(17.7656250, 3.7656250)	0.0662913	0.00001807
9	(17.7187500, 3.7187500)	(17.7656250, 3.7656250)	(17.7421875, 3.7421875)	0.0331456	-0.00023241
10	(17.7421875, 3.7421875)	(17.7656250, 3.7656250)	(17.7539063, 3.7539063)	0.0165728	-0.00002610
11	(17.7539063, 3.7539063)	(17.7656250, 3.7656250)	(17.7597656, 3.7597656)	0.0082864	-0.00006038
12	(17.7597656, 3.7597656)	(17.7656250, 3.7656250)	(17.7626953, 3.7626953)	0.0041432	-0.00036620
13	(17.7626953, 3.7626953)	(17.7656250, 3.7656250)	(17.7641602, 3.7641602)	0.0020716	0.00027890
14	(17.7626953, 3.7626953)	(17.7641602, 3.7641602)	(17.7634277, 3.7634277)	0.0010358	0.00024979
15	(17.7626953, 3.7626953)	(17.7634277, 3.7634277)	(17.7630615, 3.7630615)	0.0005179	0.00007053
16	(17.7630615, 3.7630615)	(17.7634277, 3.7634277)	(17.7632446, 3.7632446)	0.0002589	-0.00013707

6. Conclusion

In this study, we have investigated the global behavioural property (orness measure) of a popular aggregation operator BM and its two variants, namely, PBM and GBM. It has been observed that the global behaviour of these aggregation operators, mostly guided by their associated parameters, length of the inputs and interrelationship structure (in the case of PBM). This fact led us to systematic investigation of the nature of these aggregation operators with respect to each of the influencing factors and established several key properties. Further, the connection among the orness measures of these operators have also been studied and in some cases we provide the bounds of the orness level. As, the practical computation of the orness level of these aggregation operators involved

complex n -fold integral, we have taken Monte Carlo strategy to find the numerical estimate of complex integral and subsequently, obtained the numerical estimate of orness level. Based on the properties of these aggregation operators with respect to the parameters, we have investigated the behaviour of the Monte Carlo estimates of complex n -fold integrals involving different aggregation operators. We have demonstrated that the results derived from Monte Carlo strategy are intuitively more appealing. Moreover, we have evidenced using suitable examples that the proposed orness measures reveal a more plausible behavior of orness. Next, from the practical application point of view, we considered the estimation of the parameters associated with these aggregation operators from global behavioural property of these aggregation operators and developed an algorithm based on Monte Carlo and bisection method to find the approximate value of these parameters. Further, we have presented three practical decision making scenarios involving the estimation of the parameters of these aggregation operators to demonstrate applicability and feasibility of the proposed Algorithm.

Regarding the future lines of research, it seems interesting to the application of these concepts of orness to various practical decision making situations, where decision maker has a subjective view/attitude towards the aggregation process. Furthermore, it is also interesting to study how to define the orness measure by using generating function techniques. Moreover, one can extend the above study for the other variants of BM, such as, extended Bonferroni mean⁵⁸, extended geometric Bonferroni mean⁵⁹, power Bonferroni mean⁶⁰ and Generalized extended Bonferroni mean.⁶¹

Acknowledgement

The first author would like to thank Prof. Radko Mesiar for his valuable inputs. The first author is also thankful to Dr. Vikas Kumar Mishra for many fruitful discussions regarding the proofs of the results. José Rui Figueira acknowledges the support from the FCT grant SFRH/BSAB/139892/2018.

References

- [1] Dujmović JJ. Weighted conjunctive and disjunctive means and their application in systems evaluation. J Univ Belgrade, EE Dept, Series Mathematics and Physics 1974;483:147–158.
- [2] Yager RR. On ordered weighted averaging aggregation operators in multicriteria decision making. IEEE Trans Syst Man, Cybern 1998;18:183–190.
- [3] Yager RR. Families of OWA operators. Fuzzy Sets Syst 1993;59:125–148.
- [4] Chernoff H, Moses L. Elementary Decision Theory. New York: John Wiley & Sons;1959.
- [5] Arnould T, Ralescu A. From “and” to “or”. In: Proc 4th Int Conf on Information Processing and Management of Uncertainty in Knowledge-Based Systems. Palma de Mallorca, Spain, 1992:119–128.

- [6] Marichal J. Aggregation operators for multicriteria decision aid. Ph.D. Thesis, Institute of Mathematics, University of Liège, Liège, Belgium; 1999.
- [7] Dujmović JJ, Larsen H. Properties and modeling of partial conjunction/disjunction. In: B.D. Baets et al. (Eds.), *Current Issues in Data and Knowledge Engineering*, Warsaw; 2004.
- [8] Dujmović JJ, Seven flavors of andness/orness. In: *Proc of EUROFUSE 2005*, Belgrade, 2005:81–92.
- [9] Legarreta L, Lizasoain I, Pérez IM. Orness for idempotent aggregation functions. *Axioms* 2017;6:25;doi.org/10.3390/axioms6030025.
- [10] Fodor J, Marichal JL, Roubens, M. Characterization of the ordered weighted averaging operators. *IEEE Trans Fuzzy Syst* 1995;32:236–240.
- [11] Torra V. Interpreting sugeno λ -measures through $Q - p$ -decomposable ones. In: *Proc of EUROFUSE Workshop on Preference Modelling and Applications*, Granada, Spain, 2001.
- [12] Yager RR. Quantifier guided aggregation using OWA operators. *Int J Intell Syst* 1996;11:49–73.
- [13] Yager RR. New modes of OWA information fusion. *Int J Intell Syst* 1998;13:661–681.
- [14] Yager RR. Extending multicriteria decision making by mixing t-norms and OWA operators. *Int J Intell Syst* 2005;20:453–474.
- [15] Jin L, Kalina M, Mesiar R, Qian G. On some properties and comparative analysis for different OWA monoids. *Int J Intell Syst* 2017;32:1115–1135.
- [16] Zeng W, Li D, Gu Y. Monotonic argument-dependent OWA operators. *Int J Intell Syst* 2018;doi.org/10.1002/int.21955.
- [17] Filev D, Yager RR. On the issue of obtaining OWA operator weights. *Fuzzy Sets Syst* 1998;94:157–169.
- [18] Fuller R, Majlender P. On obtaining minimal variability OWA operator weights. *Fuzzy Sets Syst* 2003;136:203–215
- [19] Yager RR. Fuzzy modeling for intelligent decision making under uncertainty. *IEEE Trans Syst Man Cybern B* 2000;30:60–70.
- [20] Pérez LG, Mata F, Chiclana F. Social network decision making with linguistic trustworthiness-based induced OWA operators. *Int J Intell Syst* 2014;29 (12):1117–1137.
- [21] Oukil A, Govindaluri SM. A systematic approach for ranking football players within an integrated DEA-OWA framework. *Manage Deci Econ* 2017;38:1125–1136.

- [22] Yusoff B, Merigó JM, Ceballos D, Peláez JI, Weighted-selective aggregated majority-OWA operator and its application in linguistic group decision making. *Int J Intell Syst* 2018;doi.org/10.1002/int.22004.
- [23] Liu X. A general model of parameterized OWA aggregation with given orness level. *Int J Approx Reason* 2008;48:598–627.
- [24] Kishor A, Singh AK, Pal NR. Orness measure of OWA operators: a new approach. *IEEE Trans Fuzzy Syst* 2014;22:1039–1045.
- [25] Paternain D, Ochoa G, Lizasoain I, Bustince H, Mesiar R. Quantitative orness for lattice OWA operators. *Inform Fusion* 2016;30:27–35.
- [26] O’Hagan M. Aggregating template or rule antecedents in real-time expert systems with fuzzy set logic. In: *Proc 22nd Annual IEEE Asilomar Conf, on Signals, Systems, and Computers*. Pacific Grove, CA; 1988:681–689.
- [27] Rongxi Z, Jianrong X. A method for obtaining the maximum entropy OWA operator weights with uncertain orness measure. In: *Proc of IEEE Control and Decision Conference, China, 2008*:2325–2328.
- [28] Torra V. Empirical analysis to determine weighted OWA orness. In: *Proc 4th Annual Conf Information Fusion (FUSION 2001)*, Montreal, Canada, August, 2001.
- [29] Salido JF, Murakami S. Extending Yager’s orness concept for the OWA aggregators to other mean operators. *Fuzzy Sets Syst* 2003;139:515–542.
- [30] Liu X. An orness measure for quasi-arithmetic means. *IEEE Trans Fuzzy Syst* 2006;14:837–848.
- [31] Liu X. The orness measures for two compound quasi-arithmetic mean aggregation operators. *Int J Approx Reason* 2010;51:305–334.
- [32] Jin L, Kalina M, Qian G. Fuzzy orness measure and new orness axioms. *Kybernetika* 2015;51:712–723.
- [33] Dujmovic JJ, Larsen HL. Generalized conjunction/disjunction. *Int J Approx Reason* 2007;46:423–446.
- [34] J. Dujmović, Andness and orness as a mean of overall importance. In: *Proc in Proc IEEE Int Conf Fuzzy Syst, 2012*, pp. 1–6.
- [35] Larsen HL. Efficient andness-directed importance weighted averaging operators. *Int J Uncertainty Fuzziness Knowl-Based Syst* 2003; 11:67–82.
- [36] Alguliev RM, Aliguliyev RM, Ganjaliyev FS. Aggregating edge weights in social networks on the web extracted from multiple sources with different importance degrees. *J Intel Learning Syst App* 2012;4:154.

- [37] Aristondo O, Ciommi M. The orness value for rank-dependent welfare functions and rank-dependent poverty measures. *Fuzzy Sets Syst* 2017;325:114–136.
- [38] Carlsson C, Brunelli M, Mezei J. Decision making with a fuzzy ontology. *Soft Comput* 2012;16:1143–1152.
- [39] Yu HQ, Reiff-Marganiec S. A method for automated web service selection. In: *Proc. IEEE Congress on Service*, 2008:513–520.
- [40] Yager RR. OWA aggregation over a continuous interval argument with applications to decision making. *IEEE Trans Syst Man Cybern Cybernetics* 2004;34:1952–1963.
- [41] Yager RR. An extension of the naive bayesian classifier. *Inform Sci* 2006;176:577–588.
- [42] Beliakov G, Pradera A, Calvo T. *Aggregation Functions: A Guide for Practitioners*. Berlin: Springer; 2007.
- [43] Grabisch M, Marichal JL, Meisar R, Endre P. *Aggregation Functions*. New York: Cambridge University Press; 2009.
- [44] Grabisch M, Marichal JL, Meisar R, Endre P. Aggregation functions: means. *Inform Sci* 2011;181:1–22.
- [45] Gerstner T, Griebel M. Dimension adaptive tensor product quadrature. *Computing* 2003;71:65–87.
- [46] Kroese DP, Taimre T, Botev ZT. *Handbook of Monte Carlo Methods*. New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons; 2011.
- [47] Rubinstein R, Samorodnitsky G. Variance reduction by the use of common and antithetic random variables. *J Stat Comput Simu* 1985;22:161–180.
- [48] Kahn H, Marshall AW. Methods of reducing sample size in Monte Carlo computations. *J Oper Res Soc America* 1953;1:263–278.
- [49] Fishman G. *Monte Carlo: Concepts, Algorithms, and Applications*. New York: Springer-Verlag; 2013.
- [50] Liu JS. *Monte Carlo Strategies in Scientific Computing*. New York: Springer-Verlag; 2008.
- [51] Faure H. Discrepance de suites associes á un systéme de numration. *Comptes Rendus Mathmatique* 1978;286-A:293–296..
- [52] Bonferroni C. Sulle medie multiple di potenze. *Bolletino Matematica Italiana* 1950;5:267–270.
- [53] Yager RR. On generalized Bonferroni mean operators for multi-criteria aggregation. *Int J Approx Reason* 2009; 50:1279–1286.
- [54] Xia M, Xu Z, Zhu B. Geometric Bonferroni means with their application in multi-criteria decision making. *Knowl-Based Syst* 2013;40:88–100.

- [55] Wilkin T, Beliakov G. Weakly monotonic averaging functions. *Int J Intell Syst* 2015;30:144–169.
- [56] Dutta B, Guha D. Partitioned Bonferroni mean based on linguistic 2-tuple for dealing with multi-attribute group decision making. *Appl Soft Comput* 2015;37:166–179.
- [57] Graham RL, Knuth DE, Patashnik O. *Concrete Mathematics: A Foundation for Computer Science*, second edition. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley Publishing Company; 1994.
- [58] Dutta B, Guha D, Mesiar R. A model based on linguistic 2-tuples for dealing with heterogeneous relationship among attributes in multi-expert decision making. *IEEE Trans Fuzzy Syst* 2015;23:1817–1831.
- [59] Dutta B, Chan FT, Guha D, Niu B, Ruan J. Aggregation of heterogeneously related information with extended geometric Bonferroni mean and its application in group decision making. *Int J Intell Syst* 2018;33:487–513.
- [60] He Y, He Z, Wang G, Chen H. Hesitant fuzzy power Bonferroni means and their application to multiple attribute decision making. *IEEE Trans Fuzzy Syst* 2015;23:1655–1668.
- [61] Chen ZS, Chin KS, Li YL, Yang Y. On generalized extended Bonferroni means for decision making. *IEEE Trans Fuzzy Syst* 2016;24:1525–1543.